

ADVANTAGES OF CORPORATE IDENTITY IN A HOTEL

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Abstract. *An important stage in the development of the concept is the right choice of corporate identity of the hotel. In this article I would like to characterize the corporate identity of hotels, as corporate identity is the basis for the formation of the image of any organization. In this case we will consider the corporate style of hotels, which implies the use of uniform design principles for interiors, for all forms of advertising and all types of documentation.*

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Corporate identity is commonly studied based on several functional aspects. First, as a design task. In this case, it is reduced to the creation and subsequent finalization of the corporate block, that is, possible combinations of the logo, a set of corporate fonts and the most necessary text information. Secondly, as an element of the marketing complex, including advertising and PR. A classic example: creating and maintaining a brand. Thirdly, as an element of management. It is nothing but corporate culture.

Corporate identity is used literally in everything: in the exterior and interior design of the hotel building, in the selection and creation of accessories and equipment (equipment, furniture, textiles, decorative elements) and, of course, all types of advertising.

As an element of corporate identity can be considered such internal corporate standards as speed and quality of service, attitude to the client, sanitary and hygienic characteristics.

Many hotels prescribe such postulates in their charter. Often it becomes the basis for positioning. Most of the corporate identity media are designed for visual perception, and only a small part for auditory perception. However, in the hotel business there is a possibility of involving kinetic type of perception. Furnishings, decor and equipment of the building are direct carriers of corporate identity, and their perception is carried out not only by the eyes, so the texture and quality of all equipment comes to the fore.

This approach is undeniable from a stylistic point of view. Many hotels follow the spirit of tradition in everything, from interior design to towels and tableware. For them, the main thing is atmosphere and uniqueness. In a hotel in the "knightly" style, this is evidenced not only by the decoration: even kebabs in the restaurant will be served on swords. If it is baroque, much reminds of the era of Louis XIV. This is how the flavor is created.

The emergence of a special image contributes to the presence of "branded" services or some zest - something special that competitors do not have. For example, family atmosphere and names of famous people who once lived in the Raphael Hotel in Paris (Ava Gardner, Marlon Brando, Katharine Hepburn, Andy McDowell, Pierce Brosnan and others). Related to Vladimir Nabokov's name is the Montreux Palace Hotel (Montreux). Hotel Villa San Michele in Florence is known since the XV century as a Franciscan monastery, as well as the place where Michelangelo created (his frescoes are preserved in the hotel).

Hotel Negressco (Nice) is famous for its antique collection. The list could go on. Such hotels are proud not only of their image, but also of their famous clients. We talk about the unity of style, but often, especially in our time, in the design of the hotel there is a mixture of styles. Sometimes it is acceptable and even necessary. Thus, opening a hotel in a genuine castle of the Middle Ages in any case will require finishing with modern materials and equipping with modern technology. In this case, it is possible only conditional, decorative stylization under the antiquity.

The style of the hotel can be mixed: the classical interior is quite permissible to use modern furniture. The main thing in the design - the general line, the individual elements of the interior should harmoniously and naturally combine with each other. Eclecticism is often called the main "style" of the modern era of extra-left development of architecture. When the next fashionable trend has already "worked itself out", and a new one has not yet been created, the eclecticism prevails.

And architects turn to architectural heritage, re-learning and rethinking the accumulated experience. The eclectic style is extremely utilitarian, as it allows for the efficient use of objects and space. True, sometimes the mixing has the character of a risky experiment, where elements of the most different directions are deliberately opposed, as if colliding with each other. The most daring architectural and design solutions often cause a lot of controversy, but at the same time they form a certain image and increase interest in the hotel.

Interior design in the now fashionable "high-tech" style implies clear and simple geometric shapes, the use of "pure" colors: black, white and gray as a basis, and red, blue, green and yellow as a complement. Refusal of decorative elements: everything is maximally utilitarian. This style does not tolerate carelessness - everything should be even and smooth, in everything - the game of space and light, not ornament and color, as in the classics. Wooden or with a texture "under the tree" surface is replaced by a solid-colored plastic, and porcelain and crystal - one-color, without drawings frosted glass or glazed faience. Currently, some historic hotels are moving away from overloading the interior with details. Thus, Brussels hotel Amigo, located in a medieval building, Florentine hotel Savoy in a building of the late XIX century, Martinez in Cannes - these are simple, even minimalist interiors. In modern architecture, interior and exterior are closely connected, one flowing into the other thanks to large glazed openings and stained glass windows. In the evening the view of the hotel, its halls and restaurants illuminated from inside creates an idea of the interior, decor and interior decoration. It is an element of outdoor advertising.

In terms of interior design, we and the West have opposite tendencies. In the West, modern hotels have rather modest "business" interiors. In some countries modern high-class hotels strive for unconventionality and flamboyance in the interior design. They often use custom-made furniture, author's works as elements of decoration. Despite the many fashionable trends in modern design, hotels give preference to the classics, as it is positively perceived by most customers. Classics is characterized by simplicity, naturalness of forms and strict adherence to the principle of proportionality. This style successfully combines coziness and representativeness, it is always up-to-date and is not subject to moral aging, which is characteristic of most extravagant styles.

High-class hotels equip their interiors with high-quality furniture, use expensive materials in finishing, which does not allow them to completely renew the furnishings every few years in pursuit of fashion. Besides, with the change of style it is necessary to change the concept of the hotel. Therefore, the hotel business is quite conservative in terms of design. There are undoubtedly increased requirements to the quality and durability of furniture, textiles, materials used in the

decoration of hotel rooms. A minimum of items that can be broken is used. "Trimnings" should also not interfere with the cleaning of the room. The design is practical, based on health and safety considerations. It is decided how much space and light is needed, and whether separate storage and placement areas are required for various items. Special customer needs are also taken into account.

An important role is played by the color solution. It is known that color affects the emotions of visitors.

Nowadays many hotels in Uzbekistan follow the corporate style of the hotel: "Hilton Tashkent City", "Navruz", "Turon", "MERCURE BUKHARA OLD TOWN", "Sahid Zarafshon", Courtyard by Marriott Tashkent hotel of American brand.

Hotel "City Palace" is a place where rich oriental color and modern European design merge together to ensure that guests enjoy a pleasant time at the hotel.

I wish many hotels in Uzbekistan would follow the right choice of corporate style.

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